

Fuel Compact-wise Fine-mesh Core Calculation Method for Prismatic-type HTGRs

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ABSTRACT

The accuracy of the fuel compact-wise fine-mesh core calculation was verified as a core analysis method for the demonstration reactor design of prismatic-type HTGRs. The fuel element is discretized with triangular meshes to directly calculate fuel compact-wise power without reconstruction. Diffusion and transport calculations are used for core calculations. A fine-mesh calculation without the SPH corrected cross sections shows the discrepancy on k -effective and fuel compact-wise fission rate distribution in comparison with the reference heterogeneous calculation that explicitly models core geometry. Application of the SPH method reduces the homogenization error in both transport and diffusion calculations. The diffusion and transport methods show similar calculation accuracy in the present calculation condition when the SPH method is used.

Keywords: HTGRs, Core analysis, SPH method, Transport calculation, Diffusion calculation

1. INTRODUCTION

The High-Temperature Gas-cooled Reactor (HTGR) is a type of nuclear reactor that uses graphite as the moderator and helium as the coolant. This design allows the extraction of heat at extremely high temperatures from the reactor. Use of high-temperature heat is desirable not only for high-efficiency electricity generation but also for diverse industrial applications, such as hydrogen production without CO₂ emissions. In Japan, research and development efforts are progressing toward a demonstration reactor [1].

For the development of HTGR demonstration reactor, a design calculation method that can accurately and efficiently evaluate core characteristics is essential. A prismatic-type HTGR core contains many fuel elements with a heterogeneous structure composed of many fuel compacts within graphite blocks. While core analysis with such a heterogeneous model achieves high calculation accuracy [2], the computational cost would make it impractical as a design calculation method.

To address this issue, partial homogenization is applied to complex structures like fuel elements. However, this process approximates the detailed geometry of the fuel element, which introduces prediction errors. To reduce the homogenization error, the discontinuity factor [3] and the superhomogenization (SPH) method [4] are commonly applied. Although the effectiveness of discontinuity factors has been demonstrated [5], their implementation in existing transport calculation codes would require significant efforts. However, the SPH method can be applied without intrusive modifications to existing codes, making it practical for use in design calculations. Thus, the SPH method is regarded as a promising technique for HTGRs design calculations due to its practicality. However, it has been shown that, in the case of transport calculations for Light Water Reactors (LWRs), SPH factors may not converge or may not be appropriate values when strong absorbers exist [5].

Previous studies on the SPH method primarily targeted LWRs [4]. However, sufficient verification has not been performed for HTGRs, whose core structure and neutronic characteristics significantly differ

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from those of LWRs. Specifically, effectiveness of the SPH method applied to a partially homogenized core model, where the fuel element is divided into many meshes, has not been sufficiently verified.

Therefore, this study focuses on the homogenization error in the core analysis of HTGRs. The objective is to evaluate the effectiveness of the SPH method in reducing homogenization errors in prismatic-type HTGR core analyses. The performance of the SPH correction is evaluated for both diffusion and transport core calculations.

Hereafter, Section 2 describes the outline of the calculation methods. Section 3 explains the analysis results for a two-dimensional core model based on the High Temperature engineering Test Reactor (HTTR) of Japan Atomic Energy Agency (JAEA) [6]. Section 4 summarizes the findings of this study.

2. CALCULATION METHODS

2.1. Cross Section Correction Using SPH Method

The SPH method preserves the reaction rates of the reference heterogeneous transport calculation in the homogeneous calculation. In this method, the homogenized cross sections are corrected using a correction factor called the SPH factor. The SPH factor μ is defined as the ratio of the scalar flux in the heterogeneous model to that in the homogeneous model, as shown in Eq. (1).

$$\mu = \frac{\phi^{\text{het}}}{\phi^{\text{hom}}}. \quad (1)$$

Here, ϕ^{het} represents the scalar flux in the heterogeneous model, and ϕ^{hom} represents the scalar flux in the homogeneous model. In this study, the SPH correction is applied to both diffusion and transport calculations with triangular meshes; the former is based on a simple finite-difference diffusion method, and the latter is based on the method of characteristics (MOC) with the linear source approximation. The specific application method of the SPH correction for diffusion or transport is described below.

The SPH method in the diffusion equation is described. For simplicity, assuming the 1-energy group 1D slab geometry, the diffusion equation with the SPH corrected cross sections is written as Eq. (2).

$$-\mu D \frac{d^2}{dx^2} \phi(x) + \mu \Sigma_a \phi(x) = \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}} \mu \nu \Sigma_f \phi(x). \quad (2)$$

Here, D is the diffusion coefficient; Σ_a and $\nu \Sigma_f$ are the macroscopic absorption and production cross sections, respectively; k_{eff} is the effective multiplication factor; and ϕ is the scalar flux. From Eq. (2), the diffusion coefficient and the macroscopic cross sections are multiplied by the SPH factor. Since the diffusion coefficient is proportional to the inverse of the transport-corrected cross sections, the transport-corrected cross section is multiplied by the inverse of the SPH factor, while other cross sections are multiplied by the SPH factor.

Next, the SPH method in MOC is explained. Like the diffusion equation, assuming the 1-energy group 1D slab geometry, the transport equation with the SPH corrected cross sections is written as Eq. (3).

$$\Omega_x \frac{d}{dx} \psi(x, \Omega_x) + \mu \Sigma_t \psi(x, \Omega_x) = \mu \Sigma_s \phi(x) + \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}} \mu \nu \Sigma_f \phi(x). \quad (3)$$

Here, Ω_x represents the direction cosine, and ψ represents the angular flux. In Eq. (3), the cross sections for all reaction types are multiplied by the SPH factor, which is called the direct method [7]. In addition to the direct method, other SPH methods for MOC exist [7-8]:

- No total correct method:
The total cross section is not corrected, while other cross sections are multiplied by the SPH factor.
- Simultaneous method:
The total cross section is divided by the SPH factor, while other cross sections are multiplied by the SPH factor.

A summary of the cross section corrections by the SPH method is shown in Table I.

Table I. Comparison of cross section corrections in various SPH methods.

	Diffusion	MOC		
		Direct	No total correct	Simultaneous
Transport corrected total cross section	$(1/\mu)\Sigma_{tr}$	$\mu\Sigma_{tr}$	Σ_{tr}	$(1/\mu)\Sigma_{tr}$
Absorption cross section	$\mu\Sigma_a$	$\mu\Sigma_a$	$\mu\Sigma_a$	$\mu\Sigma_a$
Production cross section	$\mu\nu\Sigma_f$	$\mu\nu\Sigma_f$	$\mu\nu\Sigma_f$	$\mu\nu\Sigma_f$
Scattering cross section to other groups	$\mu\Sigma_s$	$\mu\Sigma_s$	$\mu\Sigma_s$	$\mu\Sigma_s$
Scattering cross section to within group	$\mu\Sigma_s$	$\mu\Sigma_s$	$\mu\Sigma_s + \Sigma_{tr}(1 - \mu)$	$\mu\Sigma_s + \Sigma_{tr}(1/\mu - \mu)$

2.2. Calculation Procedures

The SPH correction procedure in this study is as follows. The SPH factors are calculated in the single fuel element geometry or the colorset geometry with seven control-rod/fuel/reflector elements as described in Section 3.

1. Perform the reference heterogeneous transport calculation to obtain the scalar flux for each SPH correction region. This calculation is performed only once at the beginning.
2. Perform the homogeneous model calculation using the homogenized cross sections obtained from the heterogeneous model calculation. Calculate the scalar flux for each SPH correction region.
3. Calculate the SPH factor for each SPH correction region and energy group from the ratio of scalar fluxes obtained in the heterogeneous and homogeneous calculations, as shown in Eq. (1).
4. Correct the cross sections for the homogeneous calculation using the SPH factors obtained in step 3. Perform the homogeneous calculation again.
5. Check the convergence of the SPH factors and repeat steps 3 and 4 until the convergence criterion is satisfied. The convergence criterion for the SPH factor is shown in Eq. (4). Here, n denotes the iteration number of the SPH factor calculation.

$$\max \left(\frac{|\mu_{i,g}^{(n)} - \mu_{i,g}^{(n-1)}|}{\mu_{i,g}^{(n)}} \right) < 1.0 \times 10^{-3}. \quad (4)$$

3. NUMERICAL CALCULATIONS

3.1. Analysis Models and Conditions

In this study, three types of analysis models are developed for applying the SPH method: a single fuel element model, a fuel/reflector colorset model, and a core model. The single fuel element model and the fuel/reflector colorset model are used to calculate the SPH factors. The heterogeneous and homogeneous calculations for all models are performed with 9 energy groups. The energy group structure used is shown in Table II [9]. The 9-group cross sections were prepared as follows. The 361 group cross sections are generated by the general-purpose neutronics analysis code CBZ [10]. Then the heterogeneous transport calculation by the GENESIS code (2D MOC) [11] is carried out in 361 groups, followed by the energy collapsing to 9 groups and homogenization in sub-divided meshes. JENDL-4.0 [12] is used as the nuclear data library.

The heterogeneous single fuel element model consists of five material regions (fuel compact, fuel sleeve, graphite, helium, and BP), as shown in Figure 1 (a). The homogenized model, shown in Figure 1 (b),

is generated from the heterogeneous model by performing spatial homogenization within each triangular mesh. During homogenization, the fuel element is divided into 16×16 triangular meshes (total number of 384 meshes) to avoid including multiple fuel compacts within a single triangular mesh. Four types of fuel enrichments are set: 4.3%, 5.2%, 5.9%, and 6.3%. The periodic boundary condition is used to consider asymmetrical location of burnable poisons.

The colorset model is employed to generate and correct the homogenized cross sections of the control rod element. The geometry of the model consists of a single control rod element surrounded by two fuel elements and four reflector elements. When applying the SPH correction to the colorset model, the correction is applied to all seven elements. The reflective boundary condition is used.

The core analysis is performed using the homogenized cross sections obtained from the single fuel element and colorset models. The 2D core model represents the horizontal cross section at the mid-plane of the 3D HTTR core. The 2D core model consists of three types of elements: fuel elements, control rod elements, and reflector elements. It is noted that some simplifications and modifications are adopted for the 2D core model. Figure 2 shows the heterogeneous core model (a) and the homogeneous core model (b), both with control rods inserted. In the control rod inserted model, control rod elements are also placed at the irradiation column positions to maximize the impact of control rod. The vacuum boundary condition is applied.

Figure 1. Single fuel element model.

Figure 2. Core model of the HTTR with control rod.

Table II. Energy group structure.

Group	Energy boundary (MeV)
9	2.00e+01, 8.21e-01, 5.53e-03, 4.00e-06, 1.15e-06, 9.72e-07, 6.25e-07, 1.40e-07, 5.80e-08, 1.00e-11

3.2. Calculation Codes

The GENESIS transport code is used for analysis. The 2D MOC with a linear source approximation is applied to both the heterogeneous and homogeneous models. The diffusion calculations in this study are performed using the CMFD acceleration method implemented in GENESIS. Specifically, a calculation equivalent to the conventional finite-difference diffusion calculation is carried out by setting the correction term D^{cor} , which reproduces the transport behavior in the CMFD acceleration, to 0. The MOC transport calculation conditions in GENESIS adopt the optimized parameters for the 2D HTTR core analysis presented in reference [2]. The accuracy of CBZ and GENESIS for the HTTR has already been verified by comparison with the continuous energy Monte-Carlo code [2].

3.3. Numerical Results

3.3.1. Single fuel element and colorset analyses

Table III shows the SPH correction results for the single fuel elements of each enrichment. The difference of k-effective is calculated as (homogeneous - heterogeneous) / heterogeneous. Here, the 9-group heterogeneous calculation results are used as the reference to evaluate the homogenization error. In the case of the single fuel element model, the presence of the absorber (BP) did not deteriorate the convergence behavior of the SPH factors. Therefore, only the direct method was applied for SPH correction in MOC calculation. Table III confirms that applying the SPH correction results in good agreement with the reference k-infinity for both diffusion and MOC calculations.

Table III. SPH correction results in the single fuel element.

Calculation	SPH correction	Difference of k-infinity [%]			
		4.3 %	5.2 %	5.9 %	6.3 %
Diffusion	No	-0.88	-0.76	-0.69	-0.65
	Yes	-0.00	-0.00	-0.00	-0.00
MOC	No	-0.50	-0.43	-0.40	-0.38
	Yes (Direct)	-0.00	-0.00	-0.00	-0.00

Next, the SPH correction results for the colorset model are shown in Table IV. Like the single fuel element model, the 9-group heterogeneous colorset calculation is used as the reference. In the colorset model, the SPH factors for transport calculation failed to converge when the direct method was applied, which is caused by the presence of the control rod, a strong neutron absorber. On the other hand, SPH corrections other than the direct method converged, and it was confirmed that the k-effective values agreed well with the reference. Based on this result, the homogenized cross sections for the control rod elements used in the transport calculations are corrected with the no total correct method, or the simultaneous method. When the Simultaneous method was applied, the corrected total cross section in the meshes near the control rod became physically excessively large values, which is a subject for future investigation.

Table IV. SPH correction results in the colorset elements.

Calculation	SPH correction	Difference of k-effective [%]
Diffusion	No	-1.80
	Yes	0.01
MOC	No	-2.19
	Yes (Direct)	(diverge)
	Yes (No total correct)	0.00
	Yes (Simultaneous)	0.00

3.3.2. Core analysis

Table V shows the core calculation results without and with the SPH correction for the control rod withdrawn and inserted model. Figure 3 shows the distribution of the relative difference in the relative fission rate distribution for each homogenized mesh without and with the SPH correction in the control rod inserted core model. Each fuel compact is divided into 6 homogenized meshes, and the 9-group heterogeneous transport calculation is used as the reference.

In the SPH correction for MOC calculation, different correction methods are applied to each core component. The direct method is used for the fuel element cross sections. In contrast, for the control rod elements, the cross sections corrected by the no total correct method or the simultaneous method are adopted, both of which achieved convergence of the SPH factor in the colorset model analysis. The reflector elements, which consist solely of graphite, are not corrected.

When the homogenized cross sections are not corrected, the difference from the reference solution in the control rod inserted configuration becomes larger than that in the withdrawn configuration due to the presence of the strong absorber (control rod). On the other hand, applying the SPH correction reduces the homogenization error in both configurations. Furthermore, when using SPH-corrected cross sections, the diffusion and transport (MOC) calculations have almost the same accuracy. Similar verification in a three-dimensional core will be an issue for future study.

Table V. Comparison of the SPH corrected k-effective and fuel compact-wise fission rate distributions for 2D HTTR core without and with control rod.

Control rod	Calculation	SPH correction	Difference of k-effective [%]	Triangular mesh including fuel compact-wise fission rate difference [%]		
				RMS	Max	Min
Out	Diffusion	No	-1.14	0.58	2.01	-1.64
		Yes	-0.34	0.49	2.73	-1.20
	MOC	No	-0.50	0.52	1.73	-1.57
		Yes	-0.03	0.47	2.03	-1.24
In	Diffusion	No	-3.20	1.19	2.06	-5.95
		Yes	-0.01	0.78	2.06	-3.57
	MOC	No	-3.05	1.60	2.79	-7.82
		Yes (No total correct)	-0.29	0.97	2.03	-4.59
		Yes (Simultaneous)	-0.20	0.92	2.10	-4.19

Control rod inserted model
(without correction, diffusion)

Control rod inserted model
(with correction, diffusion)

Control rod inserted model
(without correction, MOC)

Control rod inserted model
(with correction: no total correct, MOC)

Inserted control rod model
(with correction: simultaneous, MOC)

Figure 3. Relative differences of the mesh-wise relative fission rate distribution.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the calculation accuracy of a fine-mesh core analysis method capable of directly evaluating the fuel compact-wise fission rate distribution was verified for the core analysis of a prismatic-type HTGR. For the diffusion and transport calculations, the SPH method was employed to reduce the homogenization error. The analysis was performed for a 2D core model based on the HTTR. The results confirmed that the SPH method reduces the errors on the k-effective and the fuel compact-wise fission rate distribution caused by homogenization. It was also demonstrated that, under the calculation conditions and model considered in this study, the calculation accuracy with the SPH correction was comparable between the diffusion and transport calculations. Future tasks are as follows: Development of a correction approach that can provide physically appropriate corrected cross sections for transport calculations, including MOC, in the model containing strong absorbers such as control rods; verification in 3D core geometry; comparison with the continuous energy Monte-Carlo method.

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